

A COMMON, OPEN SOURCE INTERFACE
BETWEEN EARTH OBSERVATION DATA
INFRASTRUCTURES AND FRONT-END
APPLICATIONS

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Table of Contents

1. Aims	6
2. Methods	6
3. Results	6
3.1. Questionnaire: Understanding user needs related to openEO	6
3.1.1. User types	6
3.1.2. Data use	6
3.1.3. File formats	7
3.1.4. Cloud computing infrastructures	7
3.1.5. Programming languages	9
3.1.6. Software	9
3.1.7. Web Service Protocols	9
3.1.8. EO tasks	9
3.1.9. Feedback on openEO and engagement	12
3.2. Use Case Workshop: detailed feedback on openEO	13
3.2.1. Feedback from user testing	13
3.2.2. Key discussion points	13
4. Synthesis	13
5. References	14
Appendices	15
A. Questionnaire	15

List of Tables

List of Figures

3.1. User types self-identified by respondents.	7
3.2. Satellite data being used or intended to be used.	8
3.3. File formats used in EO related tasks.	8
3.4. The cloud computing infrastructures that users are currently using, or have recently used, and which they would like to use as a back-end via openEO.	9
3.5. Programming languages used in EO tasks.	10
3.6. Software used in EO tasks.	10
3.7. The web service protocols and standards that were used for discovery and remote processing of EO imagery.	11
3.8. Feedback on openEO.	12

List of Acronyms

EO Earth Observation

EODC Earth Observation Data Centre

GEE Google Earth Engine

UDF User Defined Functions

1. Aims

This user requirements report has three aims. Firstly it aims to identify the user needs related to openEO tasks. Research was undertaken to establish the user groups who were interested in openEO, and to understand the data, software, programming language, and computing infrastructures which they use. Additionally the typical activities which different users need to do, including downloading and analysis were identified. Secondly the assessment aims to capture users' thoughts on its aims and objectives. Several use cases for openEO were presented to users, who could provide first feedback on its usability. The third aim is to understand the potential for openEO to overcome any barriers which users face in their openEO tasks, and to highlight recommendations for the future of openEO.

2. Methods

Two data collection methods were used. An expert questionnaire was developed (see Appendix A), and a user needs discussion and feedback session was held during the openEO Hackathon event in Vienna, Austria. The questionnaire was sent to a targeted list of respondents, who covered a variety of countries and research types. The respondents were identified by the openEO team through their extensive networks, but the questionnaire was open to all. The questionnaire was launched at the Earth Observation Data Centre (EODC) forum in Vienna, Austria (23-24.05.2018) and was open until 19.06.2018. There were 57 respondents. Furthermore, users provided feedback on the usability of openEO during a Use Case Workshop, which was part of the openEO hackathon in Vienna, Austria (25.-26.6.2018). Other sources of information were also used to refine these findings, such as ad hoc discussions with users and openEO team members, and also feedback/discussions on the openEO Github (<https://github.com/Open-EO>).

3. Results

3.1. Questionnaire: Understanding user needs related to openEO

3.1.1. User types

The questionnaire results reveal that a number of different user types are interested in openEO, and demonstrates that our questionnaire covered all the major user groups identified by the openEO team. Most respondents were either Data Analysts or Researchers, however all user groups of interest were captured (Fig 3.1).

3.1.2. Data use

Although many of the respondents used the satellite datasets which were provided as an option in the questionnaire (Fig. 3.2), the following satellites were also used by the respondents. Each satellite was only mentioned once. Satellite datasets included Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER), Pléiades (1A and 1B), WorldView constellation, Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM), The Advanced Land Observing Satellite (ALOS)

Figure 3.1: User types self-identified by respondents.

TerraSAR-X, other ESA Third Party Missions data, Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP), Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity (SMOS) Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment (GRACE), and Suomi National Polar-orbiting Partnership (Suomi NPP) weather satellite. In addition to these satellites, respondents also used products, which were derived from multiple satellite datasets, and also ground data.

3.1.3. File formats

GeoTIFF was the most commonly used file format, with 95% using this format (Fig. 3.3). Other formats were proposed by respondents, and the number of users who indicated each file type is included in brackets below. The number of respondents who added the option in the 'other' field cannot be directly compared to the numbers of those who selected options which were available as a multiple choice option in the questionnaire. These 'other' file formats included: ESRI Shapefiles (2), GML (1), KEA (2), HDF (1), BIL (1), and Geospatial Data Abstraction Library (GDAL) VRT (1).

3.1.4. Cloud computing infrastructures

Many cloud computing infrastructures were used (Fig 3.4), however only one respondent was using EURAC, which was an option in the survey. Other infrastructures were indicated by users only once, apart from FAO SEPAL (System for earth observations, data access, processing and analysis for land monitoring) which was mentioned twice. Infrastructures mentioned were Copernicus Data and Exploitation Platform - Deutschland (CODE-DE), FAO SEPAL (that uses Amazon cloud), Open Telekom Cloud (OTC), Open Data Cube (ODC), European Space Agency Research and Service Support (ESA RSS) CloudToolbox, Joint Research Centre Earth

Figure 3.2: Satellite data being used or intended to be used.

Figure 3.3: File formats used in EO related tasks.

Figure 3.4: The cloud computing infrastructures that users are currently using, or have recently used, and which they would like to use as a back-end via openEO.

Observation Data and Processing Platform (JEODPP), Copernicus Data and Information Access Services (DIAS), and their own (private) infrastructure.

3.1.5. Programming languages

A number of programming languages were used by the respondents for openEO tasks. The vast majority (95% or 54 of 57) use either Python and R (Fig 3.5).

3.1.6. Software

In the main, respondents were using software which were not included in the survey, so 'other' was the most commonly selected option (Fig. 3.6). The number of respondents who mentioned the software in the 'other' field is indicated in brackets: QGIS (12), PostGIS (1), ArcGIS (7), R (4), Geospatial Data Abstraction Library (GDAL) (7), Sentinel Application Platform (SNAP) (6), OpenForis (1), ERDAS (2), Open Data Cube (ODC) (1), Orfeo ToolBox (5), Sentinel toolboxes (1), and ENVI (3).

3.1.7. Web Service Protocols

Most users used Google Earth Engine (GEE) API (Python/JavaScript), although a mixture were used, with many users using several (Fig 3.7).

3.1.8. EO tasks

A number of tasks were typically undertaken by the users. Questionnaire respondents ranked several tasks, and the following order (of highest to lowest importance, with the average rank in brackets, where 1 is highest, and 7 is the lowest possible rank) was established:

Figure 3.5: Programming languages used in EO tasks.

Figure 3.6: Software used in EO tasks.

Figure 3.7: The web service protocols and standards that were used for discovery and remote processing of EO imagery.

1. Accessing one or more large datasets in the cloud (2.29)
2. Data analysis in the cloud (portability of existing function in e.g. R/Python on a cloud environment) (2.32)
3. Scaling existing algorithms (2.43)
4. Downloading data (3.5)
5. Visualisation of final and intermediary results in a web service (4.17)
6. Simultaneously accessing multiple cloud (4.35)

All tasks are key for some users, and all were ranked in first place by at least one respondent. Several tasks were included in 'other':

- "create scripts/algorithms to create data products for end users (farmers) or consultants"
- "guided analysis for training purposes; case studies to recapitulate training steps; Sensor fusion/combination training"
- "provide datasets"

In order to understand activities in more detail, users were asked to give an example of a data processing chain that they would like to run using openEO. A few examples can be found below, and the type of user is indicated in brackets:

- Land cover classification using Sentinel-2: data access, custom dataset upload and access, combining datasets, cloud masking, cropping, training machine learning models, predicting based on the model (**Data Analyst, Researcher**)

Figure 3.8: Feedback on openEO.

- Cloud screening, time series construction, temporal and spatial smoothing, computation of a series of indices, derivation of zonal statistics over a number of areas of interest over time (**Data Analyst, Researcher, Software Developer**)
- Sentinel-2 down-scaling to 100m, 10-20m land cover mapping, land surface phenology (**Data Provider**)
- Calculating seasonal average NDVI for an arbitrary parcel of land (**Software Developer**)
- SAR orbit correction, thermal noise correction, rad. calibration, SAR coregistration and stack generation; coherence image generation and color composite generation (MTC, ILU, CovAmCoh) (**Data Analyst, Data Provider**)
- Create time series stacks, apply time-series algorithms to detect deforestation (**Researcher**)

3.1.9. Feedback on openEO and engagement

Users gave feedback about the description of the API and a video example of a use case. The majority of users (70 and 77% respectively) found it clear or very clear (Fig. 3.8).

Questionnaire respondents were keen to engage in the project, and 71% would like to test openEO or would like to be informed about progress within the project.

3.2. Use Case Workshop: detailed feedback on openEO

The Use Case Workshop took place for half a day after the end of the 1.5 day long openEO Hackathon [1], where the users had a chance to get hands-on experience of the openEO software. Several test use cases were prepared for the users to test the functionality of the openEO and the users worked on these with the help of available documentation. Furthermore, users had the opportunity to develop the openEO at the hackathon and to discuss this with the openEO team members. A mixture of open and structured discussion sessions were used to capture feedback from various user groups.

3.2.1. Feedback from user testing

In general, users were satisfied with the performance of openEO, with few errors occurring, and most hackers were able to complete the test cases, in a reasonable amount of time.

Although the feedback from the questionnaire was that the API was clear, and that the video was clear (section 3.1.9), several of the hackathon participants noted that in fact when they started testing the openEO, they found that the documentation was not clear, and required improvement. The openEO team noted the need to prioritise elements of the documentation which required most urgent improvement. One example was that the function names could be more clearly and logically assigned. Another common comment, was that error messages do not provide enough information, and this could be improved.

3.2.2. Key discussion points

Several important other discussion points were raised:

Identification of users and their needs. There is a need to ensure that openEO meets the needs of users, and it is important that these user groups are regularly consulted on the progress of openEO. This would reduce the risk that openEO does not meet user needs. The identification of minimum functions which users require could help - this has already been partially addressed through the use cases - and additional use cases can be developed if required.

Long-term sustainability of openEO. Discussions related to the long-term sustainability of openEO focused around how openEO might attract users, when other similar products are available. In order to ensure that openEO can be maintained in future, it is essentially that a critical mass of users is reached. It is essential for users to be involved who come from both the user and developer community, and engagement of both groups is required for it to remain sustainable.

4. Synthesis

The results from the questionnaire confirm that openEO is a useful product which can support user groups who were identified in the questionnaire. openEO can be used for the tasks which respondents want to carry out, and already supports R and Python users, who are almost all users. Links to software which is commonly used such as QGIS could be a barrier to adoption for some, although this can potentially be overcome by the addition of a plug-in. The lack of

D08: Prel. user requirement

access to some data sources (for example satellite imagery and products), means that it may not fulfil the needs of all potential users.

The Hackathon confirmed the usability of openEO, in that users were able to complete the test cases, however a lack of clear documentation made its use more difficult, and several weaknesses such as the lack of standardisation across clients meant that this is currently confusing users. Another weakness was the lack of information in error messages, which was pointed out as being a weakness in other cloud computing spaces as well. If openEO could improve in this area, it would be an advantage over other potential competitors, and could attract users. Overcoming these issues can be relatively easy, and will significantly increase the usability.

5. References

[1] openEO, "Hackathon report." [Online]. Available: <http://openeo.org/>

Appendices

A. Questionnaire

Expert user questionnaire

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

This questionnaire should take no more than 10 minutes to complete.

If you are not familiar with the openEO project, please take a minute to read the [proof of concept first](#).

In short:

openEO aims to develop a solution that provides access to cloud computing platforms with available data (back-ends) to users via bindings for various programming languages (front-ends). This will make it easier to access and analyze earth observation (satellite) data, and also makes results more comparable and reproducible.

This questionnaire therefore aims to identify current barriers which different users experience when accessing and analyzing data, and to understand the potential for openEO to overcome any barriers.

* Please read our "Data Information Sheet" Which explains our data policy related to your details which are collected as part of this survey, and which will be stored according to the Terms set out in the document. Please check the box to confirm that you accept these Terms. **DATA SHEET TO BE UPLOADED HERE**

1. Your name

2. Your Institution

3. What type of user(s) do you most closely identify with?

- Data Analyst
- Data Provider

- Researcher
- Software Developer
- Student
- Other (please specify below)

If you selected 'other', please specify here.

4. Having understood the project (see the [proof of concept](#) for more information), which openEO functionality do you intend to use, and which tasks would you not use it for? **Rank the tasks by selecting 1 for the activity you are most likely to complete via openEO, 2 for the second most likely, and so on.** If you don't intend to do a task, leave it blank.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Accessing one or more large datasets in the cloud	<input type="radio"/>						
Data analysis in the cloud (portability of existing function in e.g. R/Python on a cloud environment)	<input type="radio"/>						
Downloading data	<input type="radio"/>						
Scaling existing algorithms	<input type="radio"/>						
Simultaneously accessing multiple cloud computing environments to reproduce results across datasets and platforms	<input type="radio"/>						
Visualization of final and intermediary results in a web service	<input type="radio"/>						
Other (please specify below)	<input type="radio"/>						

If you selected 'other', please specify here.

5. Which satellite data sets are you using, or do you intend to work with?

- AVHRR
- Envisat Meris
- Landsat 1-5
- Landsat 7 & 8
- MODIS
- Sentinel 1
- Sentinel 2
- Sentinel 3
- SPOT
- PROBA-V
- Other (please specify below)

If you selected other, please specify here.

6. Which file formats do you want to use in EO related tasks?

- ASCII Grid
- GeoJSON
- GeoPackage
- GeoTIFF
- PNG / JPEG
- netCDF
- Other (please specify below)

If you selected other, please specify here.

7. Which of these cloud computing infrastructures are you **currently using** in your work (or have recently used), and which would you **like to use as a back-end via openEO**?

	Currently using	Would like to use in openEO
Amazon	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
EODC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
EURAC	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Google Earth Engine	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
PROBA-V MEP	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sentinel Hub	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
NASA Earth Exchange	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Microsoft Azure	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other (please specify below)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If you selected other, please specify here.

8. Which programming languages do you use for EO related tasks?

- C
- C++
- C#
- Java

- JavaScript
- Python
- R
- PHP
- Other (please specify below)

If you selected other, please specify here.

9. Which software do you use for EO tasks?

- GeoPySpark/GeoTrellis
- GRASS
- OpenShift
- rasdaman
- Other (please specify below)

If you selected other, please specify here.

10. Which web service protocols and standards have you used for discovery and remote processing of EO imagery?

- CSW
- Google Earth Engine API (Python/JavaScript)
- OpenSearch
- TMS
- WCS
- WCPS
- WMS
- WMTS
- WPS
- Other (please specify)

If you selected other, please specify here.

11. Give an example of a data processing chain that you would like to run using openEO (include concrete tasks, such as co-registration).

12. If you have time, please take a look at the project online resources and tell us what you think:

	Very clear	.	.	.	Needs improvement
The description of the API	<input type="radio"/>				
A short video (2m 14s) showing an example of openEO	<input type="radio"/>				

13. Would you like to be more involved in this project?

- No thanks
- Yes, to test openEO or to contribute to further developments in the project (please enter your email address below)

If you selected yes, please enter your email address here.

14. Any further comments?